

Voice-Controlled Smart Home Automation Using Raspberry Pi And IoT

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Abstract

This project presents the design and implementation of a smart home automation system using a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ to enhance comfort, safety, and energy efficiency. The system enables both manual and automatic control of home appliances, particularly lighting, through physical switches and a custom-developed mobile application. Communication between the Raspberry Pi and the mobile device is achieved over a local Wi-Fi network using the Raspberry Pi's IP address. Automatic operation is supported using an LDR sensor to control lighting based on ambient light conditions, while voice commands provide hands-free control through the mobile application. Additionally, an MQ-2 gas sensor is integrated to detect gas leakage and trigger a buzzer alert to improve household safety. The entire system is programmed in Python and executed using the Thonny IDE. Experimental results demonstrate reliable real-time control, responsiveness, and effective gas leak detection, making the system a cost-effective and scalable solution for smart home applications.